

PROPOSED ILOKO INSTRUCTIONAL VIDEO IN MATHEMATICS 3

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Abstract. This study intended to propose and develop an Iloko instructional video in Mathematics 3 for use by learners in Olea Elementary School in Malasiqui District II, Malasiqui, Pangasinan during the school year 2021-2022. The descriptive-developmental method of research was employed in this study. The data gathering tools used were the second quarter summative test results in Mathematics 3 and the evaluation instrument to determine the level of acceptability of the proposed Iloko instructional video as to its content and technical design. The Percentage of Correct Response (PCR) was used in the analysis of the second quarter summative test results. The level of acceptability of the proposed Iloko instructional video was determined using the average weighted mean and rating. Based on the descriptive data analysis on the gathered data, the following are the findings of the study, The Grade 3 learners have 3 lowest mastery level in the following learning competencies: applies the commutative property of multiplication (43%) multiplies 2-digit by 1-digit numbers using the distributive property of multiplication (40%); multiplies 2-digit by 1-digit numbers using the associative property of multiplication (39.5%), The proposed Iloko instructional video in Mathematics 3 involving properties of multiplication was rated highly acceptable as to its content and instructional quality (3.55) and acceptable as to its technical quality (3.46). Given the findings, the following conclusions were drawn: The proposed Iloko instructional video can be used to enhance the performance of learners in Mathematics 3. The proposed Iloko instructional video in Mathematics 3 is highly acceptable as to its content and instructional quality and acceptable as to its technical quality. Based on the above conclusions, the following recommendations are offered for a possible course of action: 1. The proposed Iloko instructional video should be recommended for use by the other Mathematics 3 teachers, 2. The findings of this study should be used by future researchers as a springboard for similar investigations.

Keywords. Iloko Instructional Video, Performance Level, Least Mastered Competencies, Acceptability Level

1 Introduction

Mathematical difficulties are frequently characterized by cognitive deficits such as ineffective problem-solving strategies and a lack of computational fluency. The established literature indicates that mathematical achievement is not only a function of cognitive factors but it also points to the importance of affective factors for the development of mathematical achievement. In light of this evidence, the exploration of children's affective responses toward mathematics becomes a central issue. Whereas previous studies tend to research affective motivational constructs such as self-efficacy in isolation from other related constructs, the literature suffers from a shortage of research on the relationship between different affective motivational variables and their impact on mathematical achievement in different age and achievement bands.

The K to 12 Program, focuses on the holistic development of the learners, focusing on communicative competence and multi-literacies, ethical and moral development of students, decision-making, and critical thinking, creativity. This is to create a functional basic education system that will produce responsible citizens equipped with the essential competencies and skills for both life-long learning and employment.

The content standards define what learners are expected to know and; what they should be able to do (process or skills) with what they learn, and the meanings or understandings that they construct or make as they process information. Thus, content standards answer the question, "What do others want to know, be able to do, and understand" (Marzano & Kendall). Based on Math Fluency by Rebecca Davies (2015), educators and cognitive scientists agree that the ability to recall basic Mathematics facts fluently is necessary for students to attain higher-order Mathematical skills. The implication for Mathematics is that some of the sub-processes, particularly basic facts, need to be developed to the point that they are done automatically. If this fluent retrieval does not develop then the development of higher-order mathematics skills- such as multiple-digit addition and subtraction, long division, and fractions - may be severely impaired. Indeed, studies

have found that a lack of math fact retrieval can impede participation in math class discussions, successful mathematics problem-solving, and even the development of everyday life skills. And rapid fact retrieval is a strong predictor of performance on mathematics achievement tests by Librado Calub (2016).

Aware of the contribution of Mathematics to mankind and society's progress and development, it is of great importance that every learner must be equipped with adequate mathematical knowledge and skills for him to become a functional or contributing member of society. Every one of the six-member Philippine team to the recently concluded 62nd International Mathematical Olympiad (IMO) made the country proud by each winning a medal at one of the most difficult and most prestigious mathematics competitions in the world. Six (6) Filipino students won four (4) silver and two (2) bronze medals held virtually last July 14 to 24, 2021. The IMO is regarded as the toughest and most prestigious Mathematics contest in the world. The team ranked 23rd out of 107 countries' a jump from 2020 when the Philippines landed in 43rd place. The Philippine educational system is in continuous search for the best method, strategy, approach, and or/ technique to level up the performance of learners in Mathematics. The 2018 Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA 2018) showed the dismal performance of Filipino learners in Reading and Mathematics. In the last (TIMSS) Trends in International Mathematics and Science Study participated in by the Philippines, Filipino Grade 4 pupils ranked 34th out of 38 countries in math. The 2018 PISA results showed that in Mathematics only 1 out of 5 Filipino learners (19.7%) attained at least the minimum proficiency level (Level 2) in Mathematical literacy. The performance of Grade 6 learners in the National Achievement Test (NAT) has been steadily declining in the last three years, placing them at the "low mastery" descriptive level of the Department of Education. The 2018 NAT results showed that for the third straight year 2016-2018, the national average mean percentage score (MPS) in the Grade 6 NAT continued its downward trajectory at 37.44, the weakest performance in the history of the standardized examination of the DepEd.

The inferior performance of learners in Mathematics can be traced to several factors or actors/actresses in the teaching-learning process. These are, to wit: the student, his family and environment, curriculum and instructional materials, pedagogical approaches, and school management. Knowing fully well of these factors, the Philippine government boldly implemented the K to 12 Basic Education Program. This program aims to ensure that the graduates of the Philippine educational system can be globally competitive and acceptable by setting higher standards.

Department of Education Undersecretary for Curriculum and Instruction Lorna Dig Dino said among the factors that "most probably contributed to the low MPS" was the shift in the design of the 2017 NAT, whereby it specifically tested the 21st-century skills, namely problem-solving, information literacy and critical thinking of the students, as opposed to the "previous assessment framework which was profoundly competency-based, or meaning, it is based on the Basic Education Curriculum." "While the current NAT is progressive in nature, wherein the items measure varying levels of skills, the previous NAT was based on curriculum content".

Mathematics instruction is considered the mother of all learning in both the arts and sciences. It is essential in almost every field: measurement in fashion, angles in sports, technology, and economics. This perspective on Mathematics has gained more attention with the rapid advances in information and communication. Mathematics is not just computation but a tool for understanding structures, relationships, and patterns to produce solutions to complex real-life problems. Mathematics is a necessity for people of all ages to be successful in life. Despite the usefulness of Mathematics in daily life, some factors adversely affect pupils' ability to understand and apply Mathematics concepts.

The aforementioned results of national surveys and studies imply that there is more to be done to improve the performance of learners in Mathematics. To this end, the researcher feels the teaching of Mathematics needs further improvement.

Mathematics is the learning area that is most considered difficult. As a teacher for four years, it has been observed that more than half of the classes that the researcher handled have a fear or negative outlook towards Mathematics subject. Not to mention that when looking into the grades of learners, many obtain low ratings in the learning area.

As a concerned teacher, it has been observed that the learners in Olea Elementary School specifically in Grade 3 find Mathematics difficult. Learners' difficulties often stem from a lack of conceptual understanding. To this end, the researcher feels the teaching of Mathematics needs further improvement.

The researcher as a Mathematics teacher for four (4) years, intended to conduct this study to address the learners' difficulties by proposing Iloko instructional video in Mathematics 3. The researcher believed that by using this video lesson, the learners can master the lesson and gain skills and competencies.

With the implementation of the K to 12 Basic Education Program, significant reforms were instituted under Republic Act No. 10533. This law also mandates the use of the learner's mother tongue as the language of instruction (LOI). This is because of the view that a learner learns best when instruction at the primary level is in their first language or mother tongue. Another reason for the use of the mother tongue is the belief that a learner is more comfortable learning in the primary language which results in cognitive processing and conceptualization (DepEd Order No. 74, s. 2009). The idea is supported by Nolasco when he said that using the child's mother tongue makes them better thinkers and learners (cited by Junio, 2019).

In the implementation of the Mother Tongue-Based Multilingual Education as stated in Deped Order No. 74, s. 2009, a lot of challenges and/or problems were encountered by school administrators and teachers. One of the problems faced is the availability and adequacy of mother tongue-based instructional materials.

Teachers are made to translate materials they have been using which are either in English or Filipino into their mother tongue language.

2 Review of Related Literature

All of the studies reviewed by the researcher have a resemblance to the present study. All of them, like the present study, delved into the development of computer-assisted instructional materials. However, they differed in type, learning areas, the language used, and intended users.

Keyes (2015), Diego (2015), Marinas (2015), Delfin (2015), and Lucas (2015) are similar to the present study because previous researchers focused on the development of instructional materials in Mathematics.

Seaman, Allen, and Seaman (2018) and Poquet, Lim, Mirriahi & Dawson (2018) are also similar to the present study because researchers focused on computer-assisted and video learning materials.

The study of Junio (2018) and Licuanan (2016) was still considered by the researcher to have a bearing on her study considering that it developed and validated of workbook and worktext in Mathematics using Pangasinan as their mother tongue. Sarmiento's (2016) study was on the development and validation of audio-visual instructional materials for listening comprehension.

The current study supports the findings and recommendations stated by the previous researchers, notably in advocating the use of support interactive instructional materials as a new instructional technology for teachers. For example, the proposed Iloko instructional video in Mathematics 3 will be quite beneficial to them. It will not only train them on how to utilize it, but it will also demonstrate that they are adaptable to change. It will also function as a symbol of creativity. It may even help them to develop their knowledge and abilities by allowing them to use the educational materials

3 Research Methodology

3.1 Research Design

The descriptive-developmental method of research was employed in this study since it characterized the circumstances or conditions in the Grade 3 Mathematics class by analyzing the second quarter summative test results for the previous years (2019-2020 and 2020-2021). According to Borg and Gali (2012), the descriptive method is designed to gather information about existing conditions and situations during the conduct of the study. The principal aim of employing this method is to describe the nature of a situation as it exists at the time of the study and to explore the causes of the situation.

This study is also developmental because an Iloko instructional video in Mathematics was proposed and developed based on the results of the analysis of the second quarter test results during the past 2 school years (2019-2020 and 2020-2021).

3.2 Sources of Data

The researcher obtained a percentage of correct responses during the second quarter summative test results in Mathematics 3 for the last school year 2019-2020 and 2020-2021. The summative test was made by the teacher, checked and reviewed by the master teacher, and verified by the school head, whereas, the proposed Iloko instructional video in Mathematics 3 was evaluated by the Education Program Supervisor, School Mathematics Coordinators, and Grade 3 teachers. Their evaluation was used to determine the level of acceptability as to its content quality and instructional quality and the evaluation of the LRMS Supervisor as to its technical design.

3.3 Statistical Treatment of Data

To determine the level of performance of Grade 3 learners in Mathematics, an average mean percentage score of the second quarter summative test results was used. To determine the least mastered competencies of Grade 3 learners in Mathematics, the percentage of correct responses of the second quarter summative test results was used. Results are described in terms of the percentage of correct response (PCR). To determine the level of acceptability in terms of the proposed Iloko Instructional Video in Mathematics 3, LRMS for non-print evaluation instrument. The material was rated using a 4-point Likert scale and the average weighted mean was interpreted.

4 Presentation, Analysis, and Interpretation of Data

4.1 Level of Performance of Learners in Mathematics 3 Based on the Analysis of the Second Quarter Mean Percentage Score

The first sub-problem posited in this study is the level of performance of learners in Mathematics 3 in Olea Elementary School based on the second quarter summative test results for the last two school years (2019-2020, 2020-2021). The mean percentage score was used in describing the learners' level of performance in Mathematics 3.

Table 1 presents the mean percentage score of 4 summative test results during the second quarter of the last two school years (2019-2020 and 2020- 2021). Based on the general average of mean percentage score, it showed the poor level of performance of the Grade 3 learners during the second quarter summative tests.

Table 1. Mean Percentage Score of the Second Quarter Summative Test in Mathematics 3

Summative Tests	S.Y. 2019-2020	S.Y. 2020-2021
# 1	68.28	68.67
# 2	75.16	70.10
# 3	69.06	68.88
# 4	70.16	71.33
Average MPS	68.09	69.80
General Average MPS	68.95	

4.2 Identified Least Mastered Competencies

Table 2. Item Analysis Results of the Second Quarter Summative Test in Mathematics 3

Learning Competencies Curriculum Guide	Learning Competencies MELCS	Percentage of Correct Response (PCR)		AVERAGE Percentage of Correct Response (PCR)	Descriptive Equivalent
		2019-2020	2020-2021		
1.visualizes multiplication of numbers 1 to 10 by 6,7,8 and 9.	1. visualizes multiplication of numbers 1 to 10 by 6,7,8 and 9.	42%	60%	51%	Nearing Mastery
2. visualizes and states basic multiplication facts for numbers up to 10.	2. visualizes and states basic multiplication facts for numbers up to 10.	50%	74%	62%	Nearing Mastery
3. applies the commutative property of multiplication.	3. Illustrates the properties of multiplication in relevant situations (commutative property, distributive property or associative property)	45%	41%	43%	Less Mastered
4. multiplies 2-digit by 1-digit numbers using the distributive property of multiplication.		39%		40%	Less Mastered
5. multiplies three 1-digit numbers using the associative property of multiplication.		38%		39.5%	Less Mastered
6. multiplies 2-to 3-digit numbers by 1-digit numbers without or with regrouping.	4. multiplies numbers: a. 2- to 3-digit numbers by 1-digit numbers without or with regrouping b. 2-digit numbers by 2-digit numbers without regrouping c. 2-digit number by	70%	74%	72%	Nearing Mastery
7. multiplies 2-digit numbers by 2-digit numbers without regrouping.		48%	55%	51.5%	Nearing Mastery
8. multiplies 2-digit number by		47%	52%	49.5%	Less Mastered

2-digit numbers with regrouping.	2-digit numbers with regrouping				
9. multiplies 2-to 3-digit numbers by multiples of 10 and 100.	d. 2- to 3-digit numbers by multiples of 10 and 100	73%	69%	71%	Nearing Mastery
10. multiplies 1- to 2-digit numbers by 1 000.	e. 1- to 2-digit numbers by 1 000	73%	73%	73%	Nearing Mastery
11. estimates the product of 2- to 3-digit numbers and 1- to 2-digit numbers with reasonable results.	5. estimates the product of 2- to 3-digit numbers and 1- to 2-digit numbers with reasonable results .	73%	72%	72.5%	Nearing Mastery
12. multiplies mentally 2-digit by 1-digit numbers without regrouping with products of up to 100.	6. multiplies mentally 2-digit by 1-digit numbers without regrouping with products of up to 100.	70%	71%	70.5	Nearing Mastery
13. solves routine and non-routine problems involving multiplication without or with addition and subtraction of whole numbers including money using appropriate problem solving strategies and tools	7. solves routine and non-routine problems involving multiplication without or with addition and subtraction of whole numbers including money using appropriate problem solving strategies and tools.	44%	46%	45%	Less Mastered
14. creates problems involving multiplication or with addition or		42%		44%	Less Mastered

subtraction of whole numbers including money.					
15. visualizes and states the multiples of 1- to 2-digit numbers.	8. visualizes and states the multiples of 1- to 2-digit numbers.	70%	73%	71.5	Nearing Mastery
16. visualizes division of numbers up to 100 by 6,7,8, and 9 (multiplication table of 6, 7, 8, and 9).	9. visualizes division of numbers up to 100 by 6,7,8, and 9 (multiplication table of 6, 7, 8, and 9).	48%	51%	49.5	Less Mastered
17. visualizes and states basic division facts of numbers up to 10.	10. visualizes and states basic division facts of numbers up to 10.	65%	69%	67%	Nearing Mastery
18. divides 2- to 3-digit numbers by 1- to 2- digit numbers without and with remainder.	11. divides numbers without or with remainder: a. 2- to 3-digit numbers by 1- to 2- digit numbers b. 2-3 digit numbers by 10 and 100	47%	52%	49.5%	Less Mastered
19. divides 2-3 digit numbers by 10 and 100 without or with remainder.		72%		68.5%	Nearing Mastery
20. estimates the quotient of 2- to 3- digit numbers by 1- to 2- digit numbers.	12. estimates the quotient of 2- to 3- digit numbers by 1- to 2- digit numbers.	48%	51%	49.5	Less Mastered
21. divides mentally 2-digit numbers by 1-digit numbers without remainder using appropriate strategies.	13. divides mentally 2-digit numbers by 1-digit numbers without remainder using appropriate strategies.	45%	49%	47%	Less Mastered
22. solves routine and non-routine	14. solves routine and non-routine problems	41%		42%	Less Mastered

problems involving division of 2- to 4-digit numbers by 1- to 2-digit numbers without or with any of the other operations of whole numbers including money using appropriate problem solving strategies and tools.	involving division of 2- to 4-digit numbers by 1- to 2-digit numbers without or with any of the other operations of whole numbers including money using appropriate problem solving strategies and tools.		43%		
23. creates problems involving division or with any of the other operations of whole numbers including money.		48%		45.5%	Less Mastered

Table 1 presents the 23 learning competencies in the Curriculum Guide and 14 learning competencies in Most Essential Learning Competencies in Mathematics 3 curriculum and the researcher considered the competencies in which the learners obtained a less mastered level of performance.

Based on the average percentage of correct response result, it shows that there are 12 learning competencies in Curriculum Guide and in MELCS wherein learners obtained least mastery level and these competencies are the following: applies the commutative property of multiplication (43%) multiplies 2-digit by 1-digit numbers using the distributive property of multiplication (40%); multiplies 2-digit by 1-digit numbers using the associative property of multiplication (39.5%); multiplies 2-digit number by 2-digit numbers with regrouping (49.5%); solves routine and non-routine problems involving multiplication without or with addition and subtraction of whole numbers including money using appropriate problem solving strategies and tools (45%); creates problems involving multiplication or with addition or subtraction of whole numbers including money (44%); visualizes division of numbers up to 100 by 6,7,8, and 9 (multiplication table of 6, 7, 8, and 9) (49.5%); divides 2- to 3-digit numbers by 1- to 2- digit numbers without and with remainder (49.5%); divides mentally 2-digit numbers by 1-digit numbers without remainder using appropriate strategies (47%); solves routine and non-routine problems involving division of 2- to 4-digit numbers by 1- to 2-digit numbers without or with any of the other operations of whole numbers including money using appropriate problem solving strategies and tools (42%); creates problems involving division or with any of the other operations of whole numbers including money (45.5%). The highlighted competencies are the 3 lowest percentages of correct responses that served as the basis of the proposed Iloko Instructional Video in Mathematics 3.

Among the identified 12 least mastered competencies, the 3 competencies having the lowest percentage of correct response: applies the commutative property of multiplication (43%) multiplies 2-digit by 1-digit numbers using the distributive property of multiplication (40%); multiplies 2-digit by 1-digit numbers using the associative property of multiplication (39.5%), served as basis on the preparation and development of the proposed Iloko instructional video for use of learners in the said subject.

4.3 Level of Acceptability of the Proposed Iloko Instructional Video in Mathematics 3

Table 3A. Level of Acceptability of the Proposed Iloko Instructional Video in Mathematics 3 as Evaluated by the Mathematics 3 Teachers

N= 13

Criteria	AWM	DE
Factor A. Content Quality		
1. Content is consistent with topics/skills found in the DepED Learning Competencies for the subject and grade/year level it was intended.	4.00	HA
2. Concepts developed contribute to enrichment, reinforcement, or mastery of the identified learning objectives.	3.46	A
3. Content is accurate.	3.85	HA
4. Content is up-to-date.	3.92	HA
5. Content is logically developed and organized.	3.46	A
6. Content is free from cultural, gender, racial, or ethnic bias.	3.85	HA
7. Content stimulates and promotes critical thinking.	3.46	A
8. Content is relevant to real-life situations.	3.77	HA
9. Language (including vocabulary) is appropriate to the target user level.	3.92	HA
10. Content promotes positive values that support formative growth.	3.62	HA
Over-all Average Weighted Mean	3.73	HA
Factor B. Instructional Quality		
1. Purpose of the material is well defined.	3.46	A
2. Material achieves its defined purpose.	3.69	HA
3. Learning objectives are clearly stated and measurable.	3.46	A
4. Level of difficulty is appropriate for the intended target user.	3.62	HA
5. Graphics / colors / sounds are used for appropriate instructional reasons.	3.46	A
6. Material is enjoyable, stimulating, challenging, and engaging	3.77	HA
7. Material effectively stimulates creativity of target user.	3.46	A
8. Feedback on target user's responses is effectively employed.	3.46	A
9. Target user can control the rate and sequence of presentation and review.	3.62	A
10. Instruction is integrated with target user's previous experience.	3.46	A
Over-all Average Weighted Mean	3.55	HA
General Over-all Average Weighted Mean	3.64	HA

Tables 3A-3D reveal the results of the evaluation of the proposed Iloko instructional video in Mathematics 3 based on content and technical design by Mathematics 3 teachers, Mathematics Coordinators, the Education Program Supervisor, and the LRMSD Supervisor.

Table 3A reflects the results of the evaluation made by the Mathematics 3 teachers on the level of acceptability of the proposed Iloko instructional video in Mathematics 3 based on content quality and instructional quality.

Table 3B. Level of Acceptability of the Proposed Iloko Instructional Video in Mathematics 3 as Evaluated by the School Mathematics Coordinators
N=7

Criteria	AWM	DE
Factor A. Content Quality		
1. Content is consistent with topics/skills found in the DepEd Learning Competencies for the subject and grade/year level it was intended.	3.86	HA
2. Concepts developed contribute to enrichment, reinforcement, or mastery of the identified learning objectives.	3.57	HA
3. Content is accurate.	3.86	HA
4. Content is up-to-date.	3.86	HA
5. Content is logically developed and organized.	3.71	HA
6. Content is free from cultural, gender, racial, or ethnic bias.	3.71	HA
7. Content stimulates and promotes critical thinking.	3.43	A
8. Content is relevant to real-life situations.	3.86	HA
9. Language (including vocabulary) is appropriate to the target user level.	3.71	HA
10. Content promotes positive values that support formative growth.	3.71	HA
Over-all Average Weighted Mean	3.73	HA
Factor B. Instructional Quality		
1. Purpose of the material is well defined.	3.57	HA
2. Material achieves its defined purpose.	3.71	HA
3. Learning objectives are clearly stated and measurable.	3.57	HA
4. Level of difficulty is appropriate for the intended target user.	3.57	HA
5. Graphics / colors / sounds are used for appropriate instructional reasons.	3.43	A
6. Material is enjoyable, stimulating, challenging, and engaging	3.57	HA
7. Material effectively stimulates creativity of target user.	3.43	A
8. Feedback on target user's responses is effectively employed.	3.43	A
9. Target user can control the rate and sequence of presentation and review.	3.71	HA
10. Instruction is integrated with target user's previous experience.	3.57	HA
Over-all Average Weighted Mean	3.56	HA
General Over-all Average Weighted Mean	3.65	HA

The table reveals that Mathematics 3 teachers rated the proposed Iloko instructional video in Mathematics 3 involving properties of multiplication as "highly acceptable" as shown by the computed general overall average weighted mean of 3.64. The result shows that the proposed Iloko instructional video in Mathematics 3 could be an appropriate intervention tool to improve the performance level of the learners particularly in the properties of multiplication.

Taking into consideration the results of the evaluation done by the Mathematics 3 teachers per criterion Table 3A reveals that as to the content quality, the proposed Iloko instructional video in Mathematics 3 is "highly acceptable" as shown by the computed overall average weighted mean of 3.73.

On the second criterion which is instructional quality, results show that the evaluators rated it "highly acceptable" based on the computed overall average weighted mean of 3.55.

Based on the data in the table, the Mathematics 3 teachers unanimously rated the proposed Iloko instructional video in Mathematics 3 as "highly acceptable" for use by the learners to improve their performance in solving for properties of multiplication.

Table 3B reflects the results of the evaluation made by the Mathematics Coordinators on the level of acceptability of the proposed Iloko instructional video in Mathematics 3 based on content quality and instructional quality.

Table 3C. Level of Acceptability of the Proposed Iloko Instructional Video in Mathematics 3 as Evaluated by the Education Program Supervisor in Mathematics
N=1

Criteria	Rating	DE
Factor A. Content Quality		
1. Content is consistent with topics/skills found in the DepED Learning Competencies for the subject and grade/year level it was intended.	4	HA
2. Concepts developed contribute to enrichment, reinforcement, or mastery of the identified learning objectives.	3	A
3. Content is accurate.	4	HA
4. Content is up-to-date.	4	HA
5. Content is logically developed and organized.	3	A
6. Content is free from cultural, gender, racial, or ethnic bias.	4	HA
7. Content stimulates and promotes critical thinking.	3	A
8. Content is relevant to real-life situations.	3	A
9. Language (including vocabulary) is appropriate to the target user level.	4	HA
10. Content promotes positive values that support formative growth.	3	A
Average Rating	3.50	HA
Factor B. Instructional Quality		
1. Purpose of the material is well defined.	3	A
2. Material achieves its defined purpose.	3	A
3. Learning objectives are clearly stated and measurable.	4	HA
4. Level of difficulty is appropriate for the intended target user.	3	A
5. Graphics / colors / sounds are used for appropriate instructional reasons.	3	A
6. Material is enjoyable, stimulating, challenging, and engaging	3	A
7. Material effectively stimulates creativity of target user.	4	HA
8. Feedback on target user's responses is effectively employed.	3	A
9. Target user can control the rate and sequence of presentation and review.	3	A
10. Instruction is integrated with target user's previous experience.	3	A
Average Rating	3.20	A
Over-all Average Rating	3.35	A

Based on the results of the evaluation of the proposed Iloko instructional video in Mathematics 3 conducted by the Mathematics Coordinators, it could be noted that the instructional video is rated "highly acceptable" as evidenced by the computed general overall average weighted mean of 3.65.

Further, the analysis of the data on the same table shows that the factors content quality rated "highly acceptable" based on the computed overall average weighted mean of 3.73 and instructional quality rated "highly acceptable" based on the computed overall average weighted mean of 3.56.

Based on the results of the evaluation of the proposed Iloko instructional video in Mathematics 3 conducted by the Education Program Supervisor in Mathematics, it could be noted that the instructional video is rated "acceptable" as evidenced by the computed general overall average rating of 3.35.

Further the analysis of the data on the same table that the content quality was rated by the supervisor-evaluator as "highly acceptable" based on the computed average rating of 3.50. Instructional quality was rated as "acceptable" based on the computed average rating of 3.20.

Table 3D. Evaluation Results of the Proposed Iloko Instructional Video in Mathematics 3 Based on Technical Design
N=1

Criteria	Rating	DE
Factor C. Technical Quality		
1. Audio enhances understanding of the concept.	3	A
2. Speech and narration (correct pacing, intonation, and pronunciation) is clear and can be easily understood.	3	A
3. There is complete synchronization of audio with the visuals, if any.	3	A
4. Music and sound effects are appropriate and effective for instructional purposes.	4	A
5. Screen displays (text) are uncluttered, easy to read, and aesthetically pleasing.	3	A
6. Visual presentations (non-text) are clear and easy to interpret.	3	A
7. Visuals sustain interest and do not distract user's attention.	4	HA
8. Visuals provide accurate representation of the concept discussed.	4	A
9. The user support materials (if any) are effective.	3	A
10. The design allows the target user to navigate freely through the material.	4	A
11. The material can easily and independently be used.	3	A
12. The material will run using minimum system requirements.	4	A
13. The program is free from technical problems.	4	A
Average Rating	3.46	A

Data further revealed that the high acceptability of the proposed Iloko instructional video in Mathematics 3 as evaluated by the education program supervisor in Mathematics proved that the said material could be recommended to improve the level of performance of the learners particularly in properties of multiplication.

The proposed Iloko instructional video in Mathematics 3 involving properties of multiplication was also evaluated by the LRMDS Supervisor in terms of its technical design. Table 3D shows how the IT experts considered the proposed Iloko instructional video in Mathematics 3 as to its technical design.

It is worth mentioning that the criteria used in the evaluation of the proposed Iloko instructional video in Mathematics 3 involving properties of multiplication in Mathematics 3 in technical quality rated by the LRMDS Supervisor as "acceptable" with an average rating of 3.46.

5 Conclusion and Recommendation

Given the findings, the following conclusions were drawn. The level of the performance level of performance of Grade 3 learners in Mathematics based on the analysis of mean percentage score of the second quarter summative test results for the school years S.Y. 2019-2020 and 2020-2021 was least mastered. The proposed Iloko instructional video can be used to enhance the performance of learners in Mathematics 3. The proposed Iloko instructional video in Mathematics 3 is highly acceptable as to its content and instructional quality and acceptable as to its technical quality.

Based on the above conclusions, the following recommendations are offered for a possible course of action. Mathematics teachers should conduct regular evaluations of their learners' performance. The proposed Iloko instructional video should be recommended for use by the other Mathematics 3 teachers. Teachers should also propose other forms of instructional videos for effective teaching-learning activities. Validation of the proposed Iloko instructional video in Mathematics 3 should be done to establish its effectiveness. The findings of this study should be used by future researchers as a springboard for similar investigations. Teachers should address the other least mastered competencies.

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